

1 **Sensitivities of Baseline Isolates and Boscalid-Resistant Mutants of**
2 ***Alternaria Alternata* from Pistachio to Fluopyram, Penthiopyrad, and**
3 **Fluxapyroxad**

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Abstract

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Resistance of *Alternaria alternata* to boscalid, the first succinate dehydrogenase-inhibiting (SDHI) fungicide labeled on pistachio, has become a common occurrence in California pistachio orchards and affects the performance of this fungicide. In this study, we established the baseline sensitivities of *A. alternata* to the new SDHIs fluopyram, fluxapyroxad, and penthiopyrad and assessed their cross resistance patterns with boscalid. Examination of the effective fungicide concentration that inhibits mycelial growth to 50% relative to the control (EC_{50}) for 50 baseline isolates revealed that the majority were sensitive to boscalid, penthiopyrad, fluopyram and fluxapyroxad. Analysis of EC_{50} values for boscalid for 117 *A. alternata* isolates originating from boscalid-exposed orchards showed that 44, 3, 1, and 69 isolates had a sensitive, reduced sensitivity, moderate resistant, and high resistant boscalid phenotypes, respectively.. Molecular investigation of the occurrence of known *SDH* mutations showed that among the 69 highly boscalid-resistant isolates, 44 / 2, 14, and 1 isolates possessed the mutations leading to the H277Y/R, H134R, and H133R amino acid substitutions in AaSDHB, AaSDHC, and AaSDHD subunits, respectively. Some *SDHB*- or *SDHC*-mutants displayed high sensitive, sensitive or reduced sensitivity phenotypes towards penthiopyrad and/or fluxapyroxad, whereas other had low, moderate, or high level of resistance to these fungicides. . In contrast, all the *SDHB*-mutants were sensitive to fluopyram, while 10, 5, and 1 *SDHC*-mutants had a sensitivity, reduced sensitivity, and moderate resistant fluopyram phenotypes, respectively. The *SDHD*-mutant had

1 reduced sensitivity to fluopyram and penthiopyrad, but was highly resistant to fluxapyroxad. The
2 discrepancies of cross-resistance patterns between SDHIs suggest that their binding sites in
3 complex II may differ slightly and that additional mechanisms of resistance to these compounds
4 are likely involved. Ultimately, the findings of this study should lead to the rational and
5 sustained deployment of new SDHIs in *Alternaria* late blight spray programs.

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1 *Alternaria* late blight (ALB), caused by *Alternaria alternata*, *A. tenuissima*, and *A.*
2 *arborescens*, and is now considered the most destructive disease of pistachio in California. The
3 disease affects foliage and fruits and is an annual production concern for pistachio growers (20).
4 On foliage, it can be recognized by the development of large necrotic lesions and multiple,
5 expanding lesions eventually consume the whole leaf. The lesions are black in the center due to
6 the production of many spores and are surrounded by a chlorotic halo. Under optimal conditions
7 for the disease, the fungus can defoliate a tree in late summer and autumn (20). On fruits, it is
8 characterized by small necrotic lesions surrounded by a red halo. These are located on the hull of
9 immature nuts. When the nuts develop, one or two lesions can penetrate and decay the hull,
10 resulting in shell staining of the nut underneath. The staining of the shell and colonization of the
11 kernel result in a reduction of the nut quality (20). Although cultural practices, such as irrigation
12 management and pruning to increase air movement and decrease air humidity in the orchard, can
13 help reduce *Alternaria* late blight, the use of multiple fungicide applications is essential to
14 achieve adequate disease control.

15 Over the last ten years, respiration-inhibiting fungicides, including quinone outside
16 inhibitors (QoIs, registered in 2000) and the succinate dehydrogenase inhibitor (SDHI) boscalid
17 (registered in 2003), have been vital components in *Alternaria* late blight fungicide spray
18 programs. However, due to their single mode of action, the usefulness of available products in
19 these classes has been eliminated by the rapid development of *Alternaria* populations resistant to
20 them. Azoxystrobin (Abound[®]), the first QoI registered on pistachio was a highly effective
21 fungicide in controlling *Alternaria* late blight on pistachio. However, the development of
22 *Alternaria* azoxystrobin-resistant isolates carrying a G143A amino acid substitution in the
23 cytochrome bc1 protein, has affected the effectiveness of this fungicide and that of other QoI

1 compounds that were subsequently introduced due to cross resistance (4,15,16,17,18). The
2 introduction of the SDHI fungicide boscalid, effective against a wide spectrum of pathogens,
3 offered new possibilities for the control of many fungal diseases in various crops (24), including
4 ALB. SDHIs have a unique mode of action and block the fungal respiration process by binding
5 to the ubiquinone reduction site of complex II of the respiratory chain, also known as succinate
6 dehydrogenase (SDH) or succinate:ubiquinone oxido-reductase (SQR) (3,12,24).

7 Boscalid was introduced on pistachio in the pre-mixture product Pristine[®], along with the
8 strobilurin pyraclostrobin and provided high efficiency in controlling ALB even in orchards with
9 widespread resistance to QoIs (4). However, strains of *Alternaria* resistant to boscalid were
10 detected within two seasons after registration and commercial use of Pristine[®] on pistachio (1,4).
11 Very rapidly resistance to boscalid became widespread in *Alternaria* populations in several
12 pistachio orchards, thus seriously affecting its performance (2,3). Investigations of the molecular
13 mechanism of boscalid resistance in *Alternaria* showed that resistance was associated with
14 several different mutations in the *A. alternata SDH B, C, and D* genes, encoding the iron sulphur
15 subunit (AaSDHB) and two membrane subunits (AaSDHC and AaSDHD) of succinate
16 dehydrogenase (5,6).

17 Since pistachio growers continue to rely on fungicides to effectively manage ALB and
18 because of the ability of *Alternaria* spp. of pistachio to develop resistance to site-specific
19 fungicides, there is a continuous need for new and more effective active ingredients (9) to control
20 this disease. New active ingredients belonging to the SDHI group have now been discovered and
21 are being introduced into the fungicide marketplace. Fluopyram (*N*-[2-[3-chloro-5-
22 (trifluoromethyl)-2-pyridinyl] ethyl]-2 (trifluoromethyl) benzamide) was recently launched by
23 Bayer CropScience Co. (Research Triangle Park RTP, NC) and it was registered on pistachio in

1 2012. For resistance management purposes, fluopyram is labeled as products premixed with the
2 demethylation inhibitor (DMI) tebuconazole (trade name: Luna[®] Experience) and the QoI
3 trifloxystrobin (trade name: Luna[®] Sensation). Penthiopyrad ((R,S)-N-[2-(1,3-
4 dimethylbutyl)thien-3-yl]-1-methyl-3-trifluoromethyl-1H-pyrazole-4-carboxamide) (Mitsui
5 Chemicals, Shiodome City Center, Tokyo) available as Fontelis (DuPont, Stine-Haskell
6 Research Center, Newark, DE) and fluxapyroxad (3-(difluoromethyl)-1-methyl-N-(3',4',5'-
7 trifluorobiphenyl-2-yl)pyrazole-4-carboxamide), which is formulated as stand-alone product in
8 Xemium (BASF, The Chemical Co., Research Triangle Park RTP, NC) and in mixture with the
9 active ingredient pyraclostrobin in the premix Merivon (BASF), are two new other SDHIs that
10 are expected to be available for the control of *Alternaria* late blight in the near future (most likely
11 in the last quarter of 2013). Since penthiopyrad, fluopyram and fluxapyroxad are in the same
12 cross-resistance group with boscalid, the rational introductions of these new chemistries into
13 ALB fungicide spray programs would require a good knowledge about the frequencies of
14 boscalid-resistant populations in pistachio orchards and a clear understanding of their cross
15 resistance patterns with the former SDHI. Because of potential cross resistance, the same
16 mutations in *AaSDH* genes conferring resistance to boscalid in *Alternaria* populations would also
17 confer resistance to the new SDHIs, and hence render them ineffective and useless against ALB
18 in pistachio orchards where widespread resistance to boscalid is prevalent. In a preliminary
19 cross-resistance study, we analyzed the sensitivity profiles to penthiopyrad and fluopyram of a
20 limited number of boscalid-resistant mutants containing mutations in *SDHB*, *SDHC*, and *SDHD*
21 and wild-type isolates of *A. alternata* and revealed some discrepancy in cross-resistance patterns
22 between boscalid and fluopyram (3). As expected, *A. alternata* boscalid-resistant isolates
23 carrying SDH-mutations were not affected by penthiopyrad. In contrast, *A. alternata* boscalid-

1 resistant mutants carrying a SDHB-H277Y-substitution were sensitive to fluopyram, whereas
2 another *A. alternata* boscalid-resistant isolate carrying the H134R substitution in AaSDHC had
3 only a low resistance to fluopyram (3). No information on the sensitivity of *A. alternata* to
4 fluxapyroxad and on the true baseline sensitivities of this fungus to all the new SDHIs fungicides
5 is available.

6 The objectives of this study were to (i) establish the baseline sensitivities of *A. alternata*
7 isolates to fluopyram, penthiopyrad, and fluxapyroxad for a group of isolates collected from
8 pistachio orchards that had never been exposed to any SDHI fungicides; (ii) determine the
9 sensitivities to boscalid, penthiopyrad, fluxapyroxad and fluopyram for a large number of *A.*
10 *alternata* isolates collected from commercial pistachio orchards where boscalid had been used,
11 and further investigate cross-resistance patterns between fluopyram, penthiopyrad, fluxapyroxad
12 and the former SDHI boscalid; and (iii) check which known molecular mechanisms are
13 determining this resistance in resistant phenotypes.

14

15 **Material and Methods**

16 **Isolate collections.** A collection of 50 single-spore isolates of *Alternaria alternata*,
17 collected during 1999 and 2000 from commercial pistachio orchards (Table 1) with no previous
18 history of exposure to any SDHI fungicide were used for detecting baseline sensitivity of *A.*
19 *alternata* to penthiopyrad, fluopyram, and fluxapyroxad. A total of 117 single-spore isolates of
20 *A. alternata* were collected in 2010 from several commercial pistachio orchards where Pristine
21 had been used. Identification of *A. alternata* was performed according to a previously established
22 protocol (20). One-hundred symptomless buds were collected per orchard just before emerging
23 at the beginning of April. The surface of the buds was sterilized by soaking them in 0.5% sodium

1 hypochlorite (10% commercial bleach solution) for 3 minutes. Ten buds per orchard were then
2 placed on the surface of acidified (25 % [v/v] lactic acid at 2.5 ml liter⁻¹) potato dextrose agar
3 (APDA; 4 g potato infusion, 20 g dextrose and 15 g agar per liter) in one 90 mm petri dish.
4 These dishes were incubated at 27°C for 6-7 days. Per orchard, 10 different *Alternaria* colonies
5 were selected and a mycelial plug (5 by 5 mm) from each colony was transferred to fresh APDA
6 plate to get a clean isolate without any other pathogens. A part of each colony (± 1 cm²) was
7 suspended in 8 ml of sterile water to make single spore isolations. Each suspension was shaken
8 with a vortex for 10 seconds to get the spores released from the agar. Aliquots of 40 μ l and 400
9 μ l were spread on a Petri dish containing water agar medium (20 g of agar liter⁻¹). The Petri
10 dishes were incubated at 30°C for 16 h and then examined with a dissecting microscope. A small
11 piece of agar containing a single germinating spore was cut out from each plate with a sterile
12 surgical blade and transferred to an APDA Petri dish.

13 **Determination of sensitivities of *A. alternata* isolates to SDHI fungicides.** Sensitivities
14 to penthiopyrad, fluopyram, and fluxapyroxad of baseline isolates and isolates from boscalid-
15 exposed orchards were estimated in mycelial growth tests in fungicide YBA agar medium
16 (19,25) containing 10 g yeast extract, 10 g bacto peptone, 20 g sodium acetate and 15 g agar per
17 liter of medium. YBA medium was amended with fungicides at the concentrations of 0 (control),
18 0.001, 0.005, 0.01, 0.05, 0.1, 0.5, 1.0, 5.0, and 10 μ g fungicide ml⁻¹. Mycelial growth for the
19 resistant isolates was further tested at two additional concentrations of 50 and 100 μ g fluopyram
20 ml⁻¹. Baseline sensitivity of *A. alternata* to boscalid was previously established in mycelial
21 growth assays on PDA (potato dextrose agar) medium (1,4) but it was reestablished with the
22 same isolates in YBA medium as described above to allow comparison with the sensitivities to
23 the new SDHIs. Technical grades fluopyram (a.i. 97.78 %; Bayer CropScience), penthiopyrad

1 (a.i. 99.50%; DuPont), and commercial products of fluxapyroxad (300 SC; BASF, The Chemical
2 Company, NC) and boscalid (Endura, 70 WG, BASF, The Chemical Company) were dissolved
3 in acetone (fluopyram) or water (fluxapyroxad and boscalid) to obtain stock solutions containing
4 10 g a.i. liter⁻¹, and serially diluted in acetone or water. Aliquots were then added to autoclaved
5 YBA cooled to 45°C to obtain YBA media amended with final concentrations 0 (control); 0.001;
6 0.005; 0.01; 0.05; 0.1; 0.5; 1.0; 5.0; 10.0, and/or 100.0 µg fungicide ml⁻¹. The final concentration
7 of acetone in the medium was 1% (v/v). The EC₅₀ value (the effective concentration that inhibits
8 growth by 50%) was estimated for each isolate by regressing the probit-transformed relative
9 growth inhibition on the logarithm of fungicide concentration using SAS PROC REG (SAS v.
10 9.3, SAS Institute, Cary NC). *A. alternata* isolates were classified into six categories based on in
11 vitro SDHI sensitivity. Isolates with EC₅₀ values lower than 0.01 µg fungicide ml⁻¹ were
12 considered highly sensitive to the fungicide; isolates with EC₅₀ values between 0.01 and 1 µg
13 fungicide ml⁻¹ were considered sensitive to the fungicide; isolates with EC₅₀ values between 1
14 and 5 µg fungicide ml⁻¹ were considered to have a reduced sensitivity to the fungicide; isolates
15 with EC₅₀ values between 5 and 10 µg fungicide ml⁻¹ were considered to have a low level of
16 resistance to the fungicide; isolates with EC₅₀ values between 10 and 100 µg fungicide ml⁻¹ were
17 considered to have a moderate level resistance to the fungicide, and isolates with EC₅₀ values
18 greater than 100 µg fungicide ml⁻¹ were considered to have a high level of resistance to the
19 fungicide. The distributions of the EC₅₀ values for the populations were determined.
20 Associations among baseline sensitivities of each fungicide were evaluated using Pearson
21 correlation analysis (PROC CORR) in SAS (version 9.3). Resistance factors (R_f) were calculated
22 by dividing the EC₅₀ value for each isolate by the EC₅₀ of the most sensitive isolate for a specific
23 fungicide (lowest EC₅₀).

1 **Genomic DNA isolation, Allele-specific PCR (AS-PCR) and Cleaved Amplified**
2 **Polymorphic Sequence (CAPS) assays.** To elucidate the molecular mechanism of resistance to
3 boscalid, a total of 82 *A. alternata* isolates (69 highly boscalid-resistant isolates; 1 moderately
4 boscalid-resistant isolate; 1 isolate with reduced sensitivity to boscalid; 11 boscalid-sensitive
5 isolates) were screened for the presence of known mutations in all three *SDH* target genes using
6 previously developed PCR-based assays. Genomic DNA was extracted from mycelium of 10-
7 days old colonies of each *A. alternata* isolates using the FastDNA[®] Kit (Qbiogene, Irvine,
8 California, USA). The manufacturer's protocol was used with small adjustments: the samples
9 were processed 3 times for 40 seconds at speed 5 in the FastPrep[®] instrument. The product was
10 centrifuged for 10 min at 14000 g. One-hundred µl binding matrix and 400 µl slalom wash was
11 added to the supernatant. After incubation for ten minutes, the supernatant was removed and 500
12 µl SEWS-M was added to the pellet. After incubation for five minutes, spinning at 14000 g and
13 removing all supernatant, 100µl of DES was added to the pellet. This was suspended and
14 incubated in a water bath at 65°C for 15 min. The sample was centrifuged for two minutes at
15 14000 g and the supernatant was transferred to a new tube.

16 Allele-specific polymerase chain reaction (AsPCR) and cleaved amplified polymorphic
17 sequence (CAPS) analyses (5,6) were used to screen for the presence of the point mutations
18 reportedly associated with boscalid resistance. AsPCR developed by Avenot (2008b) was used to
19 test the presence of the point mutation (C to T) at nucleotide position 996 of the *AaSDHB* gene
20 which results in an exchange of a histidine at position 277 by a tyrosine (H277Y). A CAPS
21 analysis with the restriction enzyme *AciI* (5) was used to detect the point mutation from A to G at
22 position 997 in the *AaSDHB* gene that caused a change of codon 277 from the histidine residue
23 to arginine (H277R) (5). A CAPS analysis with the restriction enzyme *AciI* (6) was used to

1 detect the point mutation (A to G transition) at nucleotide position 490 in the *AaSDHC* gene
2 which causes a replacement of a histidine residue at codon 134 by an arginine (H134R) (6). A
3 CAPS analysis with the restriction enzyme *XcmI* (6) was used to detect the point mutation (A to
4 G transition) at nucleotide position 398 in the *AaSDHD* gene which causes a substitution of a
5 histidine residue at codon 133 by an arginine (H133R) (6). Portions of the *AaSDHB*, *AaSDHC*,
6 and *AaSDHD* genes potentially carrying mutations were PCR amplified using specific primer
7 sets as previously described (5,6) and specific PCR products were directly digested with specific
8 restriction enzymes according to the manufacturer's instructions. Digestion products were
9 subsequently separated by electrophoresis on a 3% agarose gel in 1x TAE (40 mM Tris acetate, 1
10 mM EDTA) buffer.

11

12 **Results**

13 **Baseline sensitivities of *Alternaria alternata* to fluopyram, penthiopyrad, and**
14 **fluxapyroxad.** In this study, a mycelial growth assay was used to establish the baseline
15 sensitivities of *A. alternata* to penthiopyrad, fluopyram and fluxapyroxad with fifty isolates
16 collected from pistachio orchards without a prior exposure to any SDHI. For comparison, the
17 sensitivity to boscalid for the same isolates was also established. All fungicides (fluopyram,
18 penthiopyrad, fluxapyroxad and boscalid) were effective in inhibiting the growth of the majority
19 of the *A. alternata* isolates. Isolate phenotypes and frequency distributions in the unexposed
20 population for these fungicides are summarized in Table 1.

21 Boscalid sensitivity tests performed on 43 *A. alternata* isolates showed that the majority
22 (n=36) were sensitive to boscalid with EC_{50} ranging from 0.011 to 0.650 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ (mean EC_{50} =
23 0.188 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) (Table 1). Four isolates (2-F52, 2-F65, 2-F67, and 2-F69) had reduced sensitivity

1 to boscalid with respective EC_{50} of 2.355, 4.357, 2.363, and 2.184 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) (Table 1). One (2-
2 F59) and 2 baseline isolates (2-F34 and 3-J11) had low ($EC_{50} = 5.148 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) and moderate
3 resistance (EC_{50} of 10.26 and 11.601 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) levels to boscalid, respectively (Table 1).
4 Fluopyram sensitivity tests performed on 46 *A. alternata* isolates showed that all of them were
5 sensitive to fluopyram with EC_{50} values ranging from 0.014 to 0.957 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ (mean $EC_{50} =$
6 0.238 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) (Table 1). Penthiopyrad sensitivity tests performed on 43 *A. alternata* isolates
7 showed that the majority were sensitive to penthiopyrad with EC_{50} values ranging from 0.02 to
8 0.463 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ (mean $EC_{50} = 0.149 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) (Table 1). Three isolates (2-F78, 2-G13, and 3-J06)
9 were highly sensitive to penthiopyrad ($EC_{50} < 0.01 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$). One isolate (2-F63) had reduced
10 sensitivity to penthiopyrad with an EC_{50} value of 2.154 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ (Table 1). Fluxapyroxad
11 sensitivity tests performed on 50 *A. alternata* isolates; twelve isolates were highly sensitive to
12 fluxapyroxad ($EC_{50} < 0.01 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) whereas 38 were sensitive with EC_{50} values ranging from
13 0.01 to 0.311 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ (mean $EC_{50} = 0.058 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) (Table 1).

14 All the isolates with reduced sensitivity, low, and moderate levels of resistance to
15 boscalid remained sensitive to the other three SDHI fungicides. Pearson correlation analysis
16 indicated that there were significant positive baseline sensitivity relationships between boscalid
17 and fluxapyroxad sensitivities ($P = 0.0137$; $r = 0.40$), fluxapyroxad and penthiopyrad ($P =$
18 0.0006; $r = 0.54$), and no other relationships were significant. Analysis of a total of 81 sensitive
19 isolates from both baseline and boscalid-exposed populations showed that boscalid had
20 significantly less strong activity against *A. alternata* ($P = 0.05$).

21 **Sensitivity of *Alternaria alternata* isolates from boscalid-exposed pistachio orchards**
22 **to boscalid and the new SDHIs fluopyram, penthiopyrad and fluxapyroxad** In this study, a
23 total of 117 *A. alternata* isolates were obtained from several commercial pistachio orchards that

1 have been exposed to boscalid and tested for their sensitivity to boscalid, penthiopyrad,
2 fluopyram, and fluxapyroxad.

3 Based on the boscalid sensitivity tests, the 117 *A. alternata* isolates could be separated
4 into 4 different phenotypes. Forty-four *A. alternata* isolates were sensitive to boscalid with EC₅₀
5 values ranging from 0.01 to 0.83 µg ml⁻¹ (mean EC₅₀ = 0.251 µg ml⁻¹) (Table 2). Three isolates
6 (4-A69, 4-B41, and 4-B31) had reduced sensitivity to boscalid with respective EC₅₀ of 1.3, 3.37,
7 and 4.01 µg ml⁻¹. One isolate (4-B54) had moderate level of resistance to boscalid with an EC₅₀
8 value of 61.51 µg ml⁻¹ (Table 2). Finally, 69 isolates were highly resistant to boscalid with EC₅₀
9 values > 100 µg ml⁻¹ (Table 2).

10 Based on the fluopyram sensitivity tests, the 117 *A. alternata* isolates could be separated
11 into 4 different phenotypes. Three isolates (4-A80, 4-A91, and 4-B17) were highly sensitive to
12 fluopyram (EC₅₀ = 0.001 µg ml⁻¹) (Table 2). One-hundred and six *A. alternata* isolates were
13 sensitive to fluopyram with EC₅₀ values ranging from 0.01 to 0.91 µg ml⁻¹ (mean EC₅₀ = 0.148
14 µg ml⁻¹) (Table 2). Seven isolates (4-B16, 4-B18, 4-A42, 4-A57, 4-A81, 4-A24, and 4-A78) had
15 reduced sensitivity to fluopyram with EC₅₀ values ranging from 1.02 to 2.93 µg ml⁻¹ (mean EC₅₀
16 = 2.023 µg ml⁻¹). One isolate (4-B20) had moderate level of resistance to fluopyram with an
17 EC₅₀ value of 22.9 µg ml⁻¹ (Table 2).

18 Out of 117 *A. alternata* isolates, 110 were tested for their sensitivity to penthiopyrad.
19 Based on these sensitivity tests, these isolates could be separated into 5 different phenotypes.
20 Fifty-one *A. alternata* isolates were sensitive to penthiopyrad with EC₅₀ values ranging from
21 0.02 to 0.88 µg ml⁻¹ (mean EC₅₀ = 0.224 µg ml⁻¹) (Table 2). Thirteen isolates had reduced
22 sensitivity to penthiopyrad with their EC₅₀ values ranging from 1 to 4.9 µg ml⁻¹ (mean EC₅₀ =
23 3.152 µg ml⁻¹) (Table 2). Six, 21, and 19 isolates had low (5.1 < EC₅₀ < 9.3 µg ml⁻¹; mean EC₅₀ =

1 7.632 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$), moderate ($10.19 < \text{EC}_{50} < 83.43 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$; mean $\text{EC}_{50} = 38.083 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$), and high
2 ($\text{EC}_{50} > 100 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) levels of resistance to penthiopyrad, respectively (Table 2).

3 Out of 117 *A. alternata* isolates, 113 were tested for their sensitivity to fluxapyroxad.
4 Based on these sensitivity tests, these isolates could be separated into 6 different phenotypes. Ten
5 isolates were highly sensitive to fluxapyroxad ($\text{EC}_{50} = 0.001 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) (Table 2). Sixty-three *A.*
6 *alternata* isolates were sensitive to fluxapyroxad, with EC_{50} values ranging from 0.01 to 0.97 μg
7 ml^{-1} (mean $\text{EC}_{50} = 0.147 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) (Table 2). Fifteen isolates had reduced sensitivity to
8 fluxapyroxad with their EC_{50} values ranging from 1.01 to 4.98 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ (mean $\text{EC}_{50} = 2.383 \mu\text{g}$
9 ml^{-1}). Two (4-A24, 4-A40), 11, and 12 isolates had low (EC_{50} of 5.53 and 5.8 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$), moderate
10 ($10.19 < \text{EC}_{50} < 91.07 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$; mean $\text{EC}_{50} = 30.747 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$), and high ($\text{EC}_{50} > 100 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)
11 levels of resistance to fluxapyroxad, respectively (Table 2).

12 Pearson correlation analysis with all the isolates tested indicated that there were
13 significant positive sensitivity/resistance relationships between boscalid and penthiopyrad ($P <$
14 0.0001 ; $r = 0.53$), boscalid and fluxapyroxad ($P = 0.0005$; $r = 0.34$), penthiopyrad and
15 fluxapyroxad ($P = 0.0026$; $r = 0.29$), penthiopyrad and fluopyram ($P = 0.0031$; $r = 0.29$), and
16 fluxapyroxad and fluopyram ($P = 0.0078$; $r = 0.26$). There was no correlation between
17 sensitivities to boscalid and fluopyram ($P > 0.1$; $r = 0.10$).

18 **Molecular diagnosis of boscalid-resistant phenotypes.** Sixty-nine, 1, and 1 *A. alternata*
19 isolates with high, moderate and reduced sensitivity to boscalid, respectively, along with 11
20 boscalid-sensitive isolates were further investigated for the presence of known boscalid-
21 resistance associated mutations in *A. alternata* *SDH B* (*AaSDHB*), *SDH C* (*AaSDHC*), and *SDH*
22 *D* (*AaSDHD*) genes using previously developed PCR assays. Out of the 11 boscalid-sensitive
23 isolates, 9 as expected did not carry any known mutations in *AaSDHB*, *AaSDHC*, or *AaSDHD*

1 genes, and were designated as genotype 1. Noticeably, three highly boscalid-resistant isolates (4-
2 A43, 4-A38, and 4-A84) and the isolate (4-B31) with reduced sensitivity to boscalid were also
3 designated as genotype 1 since they did not carry any known mutations in *AaSDHB*, *AaSDHC*,
4 or *AaSDHD* genes. Based on the presence of specific mutations in *AaSDHB*, *AaSDHC*, and
5 *AaSDHD* genes, the remaining 66 highly boscalid-resistant isolates and the isolate (4-B54) with
6 moderate resistance to boscalid were separated in 5 different genotypes. Forty-seven of the 66
7 highly boscalid-resistant isolates and the isolate with moderate resistance to boscalid (4-B54)
8 possessed the mutations leading to H277Y (n=48) amino acid substitution in *AaSDHB* (*SDHB*-
9 H277Y mutants) and were designated as genotype 2. Two highly boscalid-resistant isolates (4-
10 B12 and 4-B19) had the H277R amino acid substitution in *AaSDHB* (*SDHB*-H277R mutants)
11 and were designated as genotype 3.. Fourteen highly boscalid-resistant isolates had a mutation
12 leading to the H134R substitution in *AaSDHC* (*SDHC*-H134R mutants) and were designated as
13 genotype 4. Noticeably, two boscalid-sensitive isolates (4-B37 and 4-A79) also possessed the
14 H134R substitution in *AaSDHC* and were also designated as genotype 4. Two isolates (4-A28
15 and 4-A33) carried both the *SDHB*-H277Y and *SDHC*-H134R amino acid alterations and were
16 designated as genotype 5. Finally, one highly boscalid-resistant isolate (4-A78), possessed a
17 mutation leading to the H133R substitution in *AaSDHD* (*SDHD*-H133R mutant) and was
18 designated as genotype 6. All the boscalid phenotypes and associated *SDH* mutations are
19 presented in Table 2.

20 **Impacts of *SDH* mutations on the fungicidal activities of fluopyram, penthiopyrad**
21 **and fluxapyroxad and their cross resistance patterns with boscalid.** To assess the impact of
22 *SDH* mutations on the fungicidal activities of the new SDHIs fluopyram, penthiopyrad, and
23 fluxapyroxad and their cross resistance with boscalid, the 82 boscalid-resistant and –sensitive

1 isolates in the respective genotype (1 to 5), as designated above, were also tested for their
2 sensitivities against the new SDHI fungicides fluopyram, penthiopyrad, and fluxapyroxad.

3 All the isolates in the genotype-1 group of isolates, including the 9 boscalid-sensitive
4 isolates ($2 < R_f < 60$), the three (4-A43, 4-A38, and 4-A84) and one (4-B31) mutants with high
5 resistance ($R_f > 10000$) and reduced sensitivity ($R_f = 401$) to boscalid, respectively, were found
6 to be sensitive to fluopyram. The R_f values ranged from 10 to 660 (Table 3). Eight of the 9
7 boscalid-sensitive isolates in the genotype-1 were also sensitive to penthiopyrad ($1.5 < R_f < 12.5$).
8 Two highly boscalid-resistant isolates (4-A38, and 4-A84) ($R_f > 10000$) were also highly
9 resistant to penthiopyrad ($R_f > 5000$), while the isolate 4-A43 remained sensitive to this
10 fungicide ($R_f = 6.5$) (Table 3). The isolates 4-A43, and 4-A84 and seven boscalid-sensitive
11 isolates were sensitive to fluxapyroxad ($1 < R_f < 130$), whereas two isolates (4-A17 and 4-A90)
12 were highly sensitive to this fungicide ($R_f = 1$) (Table 3).

13 The 48 boscalid-resistant isolates ($R_f = 6151$ and > 10000) in the designated genotype 2
14 (SDHB-H277Y mutants) showed different levels of sensitivity to fluopyram. The R_f values
15 ranged from 1 to 480 (Table 3). These 48 boscalid-resistant isolates in the genotype 2 displayed
16 different levels of sensitivity and cross resistance with penthiopyrad, with R_f values ranging
17 from 2 to 5000. For instance, the boscalid-resistant mutants 4-A60, 4-A72, 4-A44, 4-B43, 4-A51,
18 and 4-A61 had high level of resistance to boscalid ($R_f > 10000$), but their respective R_f value
19 against penthiopyrad was 9, 29, 88, 656, 2294, and >5000 . Similarly, the 48 boscalid-resistant
20 isolates in the genotype 2 displayed different sensitivity and cross resistance patterns to
21 fluxapyroxad. The R_f values ranged from 20 to > 100000 (Table 3). For instance, the boscalid-
22 resistant mutants 4-A16, 4-A51, 4-A39, 4-A36, 4-B43, and 4-A72 had high level of resistance to

1 boscalid ($R_f > 10000$), but their respective R_f value against fluxapyroxad was 20, 90, 890, 3260,
2 22060, and >100000 .

3 Concerning the two SDHB-H277R mutants (4-B12 and 4-B19) in the genotype 3, which
4 were highly boscalid-resistant mutants ($R_f > 10000$), both showed sensitivity to fluopyram ($R_f =$
5 100 and 120, penthiopyrad ($R_f = 44$ for 4-B12), and fluxapyroxad ($R_f = 20$ and 60) (Table 3).

6 The 14 highly boscalid-resistant isolates, designated as SDHC-H134R mutants (genotype
7 4) displayed different sensitivity and levels of cross resistance to fluopyram. The R_f values
8 ranged from 20 to 22900 (Table 3). For instance, the boscalid-resistant mutants 4-A49, 4-A56, 4-
9 B18, 4-A81, and 4-B20 had high level of resistance to boscalid ($R_f > 10000$), but their respective
10 R_f value against fluopyram was 20, 290, 1520, 2240, and 22900. Similarly, these type-4-
11 genotype mutants showed different patterns of sensitivity and cross resistance to penthiopyrad
12 and fluxapyroxad. The R_f values ranged from 112 to 5000, and 1 to > 100000 for penthiopyrad
13 and fluxapyroxad, respectively (Table 3). The two SDHC-H134R mutants (4-B37 and 4-A79),
14 which were sensitive to boscalid ($R_f = 9$ and 80), were also sensitive to fluopyram ($R_f = 30$ and
15 50), penthiopyrad ($R_f = 11$ and 21.5), and fluxapyroxad ($R_f = 10$ and 160) (Table 3).

16 The two mutants (4-A28 and 4-A33), which carried both the SDHB-H277Y and SDHC-
17 H134R alterations (genotype 5) were sensitive to fluopyram ($R_f = 80$ and 150), but showed cross
18 resistance to penthiopyrad ($R_f = 2116$ for 4-A28) and fluxapyroxad ($R_f = 1250$ for 4-A28 and
19 >100000 for 4-A33).

20 Finally, the SDHD-H133R mutant (4-A78), which was highly resistant to boscalid ($R_f >$
21 10000) and designated as genotype 6 showed cross resistance to fluopyram ($R_f = 2930$) and
22 fluxapyroxad boscalid ($R_f > 100000$), but a lower resistance factor (245) was obtained for
23 penthiopyrad (Table 3).

1 **Frequencies of SDHIs resistance in pistachio orchards.** Boscalid resistance was
2 detected in all the pistachio orchards. Overall, the frequency of highly boscalid-resistant
3 phenotypes was predominant in the *A. alternata* population. The two highest frequencies for
4 boscalid resistance were observed in pistachio orchards located in Madera (84.4%) and at an
5 unknown location (88.9%) (Table 4). Different phenotypes were observed for penthiopyrad and
6 fluxapyroxad and at different proportions. By comparison, the frequencies of highly resistant
7 isolates to penthiopyrad and fluxapyroxad were lower and were 18.7 and 12.5% in Madera,
8 respectively for penthiopyrad and fluxapyroxad while they were at 16.7 and 11.1% at the
9 unknown location for penthiopyrad and fluxapyroxad, respectively (Table 4). There were no
10 highly resistant isolates to fluopyram (Table 4). The SDHB mutations were the most prevalent in
11 the *A. alternata* boscalid-resistant populations at the various locations (Table 4).

12

13 **Discussion**

14 The performance of boscalid-containing product for controlling *Alternaria* late blight of
15 pistachio has been seriously reduced due to the development of *Alternaria alternata* populations
16 resistant to boscalid, concomitantly with the widespread occurrence of *Alternaria* strobilurin-
17 resistant isolates across California pistachio orchards (1,2,3,4,15). Recently, new SDHI
18 fungicides such as fluopyram, penthiopyrad, and fluxapyroxad have been introduced into the
19 marketplace. For new chemical fungicides, establishment of baseline sensitivity of plant
20 pathogens, against which future changes can be measured, is essential for estimating the risk of
21 resistance development against particular chemical groups of fungicides (21). In this study we
22 first established the baseline sensitivity profiles to penthiopyrad, fluopyram and fluxapyroxad of
23 *A. alternata* isolates originating from commercial pistachio orchards that had never been exposed

1 to boscalid or any of the new SDHIs, and compared them to boscalid sensitivity data obtained for
2 the same isolates. Correlation analyses indicated that there were significant positive baseline
3 sensitivity relationships between boscalid and fluxapyroxad sensitivities and fluxapyroxad and
4 penthiopyrad sensitivities, whereas no other relationships were significant. Differential
5 sensitivity, positive, or lack of correlation among baseline population of fungal pathogens to
6 several SDHI fungicides have been observed in other studies (10,11,26,27). Further comparison
7 of the sensitivity values obtained for sensitive isolates from both baseline- and boscalid-exposed
8 populations showed that boscalid had significantly lower activity against *A. alternata* than the
9 new benzamide and pyrazole carboxamides.

10 Another important objective of this study was to assess the potential impact of boscalid
11 resistance and associated mutations on the performance of the new SDHIs and to get more
12 insight in their cross resistance patterns with boscalid. Results of sensitivity tests for several field
13 isolates originating from commercial orchards that have been exposed to only boscalid showed
14 that highly boscalid-resistant phenotypes were prevalent in the sampled *A. alternata* population.
15 Molecular investigation of the occurrence of known *SDH*-mutations in the boscalid-resistant
16 phenotypes showed the occurrence of different genotypes based upon the presence of mutations
17 in their *SDH* target genes. *A. alternata* boscalid-resistant mutants mainly harbored amino acid
18 substitutions in subunits AaSDHB (H277Y, H277R) (genotype 2, genotype 3) (5) and AaSDHC
19 (H134R) (genotype 4) (6), with H277Y being predominant as previously reported (3,5,6). Only
20 one isolate had the H133R change in AaSDHD (genotype 6) (6). Two mutants were found to
21 carry both the SDHB-H277Y and SDHC-H134R alterations and they were designated as
22 genotype 5. The sensitivities to fluopyram, penthiopyrad, and fluxapyroxad of the described
23 genotypes were then assessed, and depending upon the fungicide and the attributed genotype,

1 different sensitivities and levels of cross-resistance between boscalid and the new SDHIs were
2 observed.

3 The *A. alternata* boscalid-resistant isolates displaying the SDHB-H277Y alteration
4 (genotype 2) showed low, moderate, or high levels of resistance to penthiopyrad. Similarly, some
5 boscalid-resistant mutants with the SDHB-H277Y (genotype 2) showed low, moderate, or high
6 levels of resistance to fluxapyroxad. The obtained results demonstrated that the SDHB-H277Y
7 alteration confer a positive cross resistance pattern between boscalid and the SDHIs
8 penthiopyrad and fluxapyroxad, although lower resistance factors for penthiopyrad and
9 fluxapyroxad were observed for some mutants. These results are in agreement with several
10 previous studies that revealed differential levels of cross resistance within and between
11 structurally different SDHI fungicides in diverse uncharacterized or SDHB-H277Y mutants of
12 several other plant-pathogenic fungi (3,7,13,14,28,29). Interestingly, the results also showed that
13 some SDHB-H277Y boscalid-resistant mutants (genotype 2) were sensitive to penthiopyrad.
14 Similarly, some SDHB-H277Y boscalid-resistant mutants were sensitive to fluxapyroxad. These
15 results are in agreement with those from a recent study showing that *A. alternata* isolates from
16 pistachio with SDHB-H277Y alteration were resistant to boscalid, but few mutants with this
17 genotype were still sensitive to boscalid (23). The absence of cross-resistance between boscalid
18 and penthiopyrad among uncharacterized isolates that have developed resistance to boscalid or
19 SDHB-H277Y mutants have been reported in *Alternaria solani* (11; Mallik et al, unpublished
20 data). The lack of cross-resistance among some *A. alternata* SDHB-H277Y mutants when
21 comparing their sensitivity of boscalid-resistant isolates to penthiopyrad and fluxapyroxad,
22 indicates that described H277Y mutation in SDHB subunit that confer resistance to boscalid (5)
23 do not always confer resistance to penthiopyrad and fluxapyroxad and that their binding site on

1 complex II may slightly differ from that of boscalid (22). This also means that additional amino
2 acid residues at different codons in SDH subunits are targeted by the latter two fungicides, and
3 thus additional mechanisms of resistance are likely involved. Two *A. alternata* boscalid-resistant
4 isolates that displayed the SDHB-H277R mutations (genotype 3) were sensitive to penthiopyrad
5 and fluxapyroxad. The absence or lack of cross-resistance between the SDHI fungicides boscalid
6 and penthiopyrad among some SDHB-H277R mutants that have developed resistance to
7 boscalid, have been reported in other fungi (7,11). Lack of cross resistance between boscalid and
8 fluxapyroxad among some SDHB-H277R mutants that have developed resistance to boscalid,
9 have been reported in *Botrytis cinerea* (28). The obtained results indicate that the described
10 H277R amino acid substitution in SDHB subunit that confer resistance to boscalid do not always
11 affect the binding, thus the fungicidal activities of penthiopyrad and fluxapyroxad (7). Regarding
12 the fungicidal activity of fluopyram on the boscalid-resistant isolates possessing the SDHB-
13 H277Y (genotype 2) and SDHB-H277R (genotype 3) alterations, our results showed that all
14 these *SDHB* genotypes remained sensitive to fluopyram. Lack of cross resistance between
15 boscalid and fluopyram in boscalid-resistant mutants carrying *SDHB* mutations has been
16 reported in several other fungal species (7,11,13,22,28). This indicates that the described H277Y
17 and H277R amino acid substitutions in SDHB subunit that confer resistance to boscalid do not
18 affect but rather increase the binding of fluopyram thus its fungicidal activity, and this may be
19 linked to the molecular structure of this benzamide derivative and its interaction with SDHB
20 (5,13,14,28). Amino acid alterations at similar or different codons in the SDHB subunit have
21 been showed to confer low to moderate levels of resistance to fluopyram in moderately or highly
22 boscalid-resistant isolates of *Botrytis cinerea* or *Mycosphaerella graminicola* (22,28), and the

1 existence of such SDHB alterations in yet to be discovered fluopyram resistant phenotypes in *A.*
2 *alternata* from pistachio orchards cannot be excluded.

3 Some *A. alternata* boscalid-resistant SDHC-H134R mutants (genotype 4) showed low,
4 moderate, and high levels of resistance to penthiopyrad. Similarly, some boscalid-resistant
5 SDHC-H134R mutants (genotype 4) showed low, moderate, or high levels of resistance to
6 fluxapyroxad. The obtained results demonstrated that the SDHC-H134R alteration can confer a
7 positive cross resistance pattern between boscalid and the SDHIs penthiopyrad and
8 fluxapyroxad, although lower resistance factors were observed for penthiopyrad and
9 fluxapyroxad in some mutants. These results are in agreement with other previous studies that
10 revealed differential levels of cross resistance between structurally different SDHI fungicides in
11 SDHC-mutants of some plant-pathogenic fungi (3,22). Analysis of the effect of fluopyram on the
12 14 *A. alternata* SDHC-H134R mutants that were resistant to boscalid showed that three and one
13 SDHC-H134R mutants had reduced sensitivity and moderate resistant phenotypes to fluopyram,
14 respectively. In contrast to a previous study, where we reported that boscalid-resistant isolates
15 with the H134R-SDHC alteration expressed low level of resistance to fluopyram (3), it is clear
16 here that this alteration also confers moderate level of resistance to fluopyram. Positive cross
17 resistance between boscalid and fluopyram in SDHC mutants of fungal species has been
18 previously reported (3,22). Curiously, among the 14 *A. alternata* SDHC-mutants that were
19 resistant to boscalid, several remained sensitive to fluopyram. These results are in agreement
20 with those from a recent study showing that *A. alternata* isolates from pistachio with SDHB-
21 H134R alteration were resistant to boscalid, but few mutants with this genotype were still
22 sensitive to boscalid (23). Some *Alternaria solani* boscalid-resistant isolates with SDHC-H134R
23 substitution were found sensitive to penthiopyrad (Mallik et al, unpublished data). Our results

1 further showed that two *A. alternata* isolates that had the H134R alteration in SDHC subunit
2 remained sensitive not only to fluopyram, but to the 3 other SDHI fungicides. The absence and
3 discrepancies of cross-resistance patterns between boscalid and fluopyram observed in the
4 SDHC mutants suggest that the SDHC-H134R amino acid substitution that confer resistance to
5 boscalid (6) do not always result in a loss of sensitivity to fluopyram. This further implies that
6 the fluopyram binding site in complex II may slightly differ from that of boscalid and that there
7 might be additional amino acid residues in *A. alternata* SDH subunits in these mutants that are
8 potentially and/or specifically targeted by fluopyram, thus resulting in a fluopyram sensitive
9 phenotype. This also supports the existence of additional mechanisms of resistance (22).

10 In this study, only 1 *A. alternata* isolate carried the SDHD-H133R alteration (genotype
11 6). The low frequency of *A. alternata* isolates carrying this type of mutation could be explained
12 by the fitness penalty associated with SDHD mutants (6). This SDHD mutant showed cross
13 resistance between boscalid and the new SDHIs, but lower resistance factors were observed for
14 fluopyram and penthiopyrad. These results are in agreement with several previous studies that
15 revealed differential levels of cross resistance between structurally different SDHI fungicides in
16 diverse SDHD-mutants of some plant-pathogenic fungi (3,22; Mallik et al, unpublished data).

17 In summary, the research presented here provided some critical information about the
18 frequencies of boscalid-resistant isolates in *A. alternata* populations from pistachio orchards at
19 several locations in California, allowed us to establish the baseline sensitivity data to new
20 SDHIs, study their cross resistance relationships with boscalid, and assess the impact of SDH
21 mutations on their performance. Overall, the baseline sensitivity data, the lack and the different
22 levels of cross resistance between SDHIs presented here will have important implications for the
23 rational and sustained deployment of the new SDHI fungicides into ALB fungicide spray

1 programs. Even though the boscalid-resistant mutants were sensitive or displayed reduced
2 sensitivity, low, moderate or high resistance to penthiopyrad and fluxapyroxad, it is expected that
3 the performance of these two fungicides will eventually be affected since mutants with fully
4 cross resistance to these fungicides will be selected and will eventually prevail in situations of
5 prolonged SDHI exposure, while the sensitive ones will be eliminated (21,27). In light of these
6 findings, penthiopyrad and fluxapyroxad fungicides should not be used in the same spray
7 program or in pistachio orchards where resistance to boscalid is established, when they become
8 registered in pistachio. Regarding fluopyram, the lack of cross resistance observed between
9 boscalid and fluopyram, particularly in the case of the SDHB mutants, seems consistent with the
10 excellent efficacy provided thus far by fluopyram against *Alternaria* late blight as observed in
11 experimental orchards where Luna products had been used, or in commercial orchards where
12 high levels of boscalid resistance in *A. alternata* have been detected (Avenot et Michailides,
13 unpublished data). However, because of the detection in this study of *A. alternaria* SDHC and
14 SDHD mutants showing cross resistance between boscalid and fluopyram, the use of these two
15 SDHI fungicides in the same spray program or in pistachio orchards where resistance to boscalid
16 is established should be also avoided. Continuous monitoring of variation in fluopyram
17 sensitivity in *A. alternata* populations from pistachio orchards where growers have started to
18 apply Luna products will be required and this might lead to the detection of additional *A.*
19 *alternata* fluopyram-resistant phenotypes. Subsequent sequencing of *SDH* genes in such
20 phenotypes could lead to the characterization of unknown mutations potentially associated with
21 resistance. Information that will be generated from such monitoring studies will also help
22 determine which commercial pistachio orchards will be at risk for resistance development and
23 will subsequently help to cope with eventual fluopyram resistance problems by developing

1 applicable anti-resistance management strategies. Future studies involving inoculation of isolates
2 with different phenotypes/genotypes onto detached pistachio leaves will also assess their fitness
3 and impact on disease control.

4

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8

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